

REFLECTIVE COMPETENCE AS A NECESSARY CONDITION FOR PREPARING STUDENTS TO PROFESSIONAL TEACHING

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Abstract:

The article substantiates the need to consider the concept of reflective competence as one of the key competencies of professional pedagogical education, reveals the essence and component composition of the reflective competence of a teacher training institute student, a future school teacher.

Key words: pedagogical activity, professional pedagogical activity, reflective competence, reflective culture.

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In the process of updating modern society, education is increasingly focused on the affirmation of the personal active principle in a person, that is, on such a person who not only possesses a certain amount of knowledge and is prepared for the competent performance of professional activities, but is also capable of further self-improvement, self-development and self-realization in it.

Thus, education performs a number of basic functions for an individual, society and the state. This shows its universal character. Students of the Pedagogical Institute - future school teachers - receive professional education. The trend associated with the priority of the personal, active principle presupposes the orientation of students in the field of knowledge about themselves, about their educational needs, opportunities and abilities, knowledge about one's personal potential and possible routes for its implementation and development in the process of professional education. Preparation for professional teaching activities also involves the formation of skills to correlate one's professional actions with the capabilities and individual characteristics of students, and to predict the consequences of one's actions in practical teaching activities.

At the same time, students, as future teachers, must master techniques for updating their students' personal knowledge. Therefore, the question arises about the need to develop reflexive competence among students of a pedagogical institute.

Reflexive competence, as defined by S. Yu. Stepanov, is "a professional quality of an individual that allows the most effective and adequate implementation of reflexive processes, the implementation of reflexive ability, which ensures development and self-development, promotes a creative approach in professional activity, achieving its maximum effectiveness".

1. In reflexive psychology, reflexive competence is presented as a complex formation consisting of various types of reflection: cooperative, built on knowledge of the role structure and positional organization of collective interaction; communicative, based on

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ideas about the inner world of another person and the reasons for his actions; personal, which is based on actions, behavior and images of one's own "I"; intellectual, which operates with knowledge about the object and methods of action with it.

In management psychology, this concept is currently understood as the ability to regulate mental activity.

I. E. Elina, considering the issue of the reflexive competence, believes that its essence lies in the awareness of one's calling and its implementation, as well as in the recognition of the social value of the result of one's activities on the basis of a deep, comprehensive analysis. The author concludes that in this case, the reflexive competence finds its manifestation in the analysis of activities both in content and in the method of its implementation, manifesting itself both from the position of "what do I want?" and from the position of "what can I?"

2. Along with the concept of reflexive competence, the concept of "reflective culture" is also used in psychology. M. V. Lukyanova, considering the reflexive culture of the individual as a psychological phenomenon, includes in this concept the ability to creatively comprehend and overcome problematic situations, get out of internal conflict states, the ability to acquire new meanings and values, enter into new non-standard communication systems, plan one's own activities and manage it. Reflective culture presupposes the ability of an individual, on the basis of free choice and responsibility for it, to carry out self-diagnosis for the purposes of self-knowledge, self-development and creative transformation of one's own activities.

The development of reflective culture as an integral personality quality consists in cultivating such dynamic components as reflective readiness, reflective competence, reflective-creative potential and reflective ability. It can be assumed that the level of development of a person's reflexive culture is manifested in the depth of rethinking of one's own experience and the degree of readiness to plan one's activities.

3. In pedagogy, the concept of "reflective culture" is used by V. A. Slastenin, exploring the reflexive components of pedagogical activity. The scientist identifies the concept of reflexive culture and characterizes it as a system-forming factor of professionalism, determined by the totality of the ability, methods and strategies that ensure awareness and overcoming of stereotypes of a teacher's personal experience and activities through their rethinking, promotion of innovations leading to overcoming problematic situations that arise in the process of solving professional pedagogical problems.

4. If we approach the consideration of the concepts of "reflective culture" and "reflective competence" from the point of view of levels of education, then, according to B. S. Gershunsky, the second can be considered as a component of the first.

5. Based on the nature of pedagogical activity, Yu. K. Babansky, N. V. Kuzmina, Yu. N. Kulyutkin, M. I. Lukyanova, V. A. Sukhomlinsky, V. A. Slastenin consider reflexivity one of the professionally significant personal qualities any practicing teacher. The basis of a teacher's reflexivity is pedagogical reflection, which allows the use of such characteristics of reflection as comprehension and awareness of the forms and prerequisites of human thinking, substantive consideration of knowledge, critical analysis of its content and methods of knowledge, self-knowledge in relation to pedagogical activity. The development of a teacher's reflective position is one of the conditions for his psychological and pedagogical competence, as it allows the teacher to put himself in the position of a student, see and evaluate his difficulties through his eyes, predict the forms of help that are necessary and significant for him, and makes it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of feedback.

6. Based on the considered approaches to defining reflexive competence, we can, in our opinion, conclude that this concept is used in relation to adult education, mainly within the

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framework of the concept of professional competence. Based on this, reflexive competence. It is advisable to include competence among the key competencies in the system of professional pedagogical education.

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